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Entrepreneurship Mindsets As Correlates Of Startup Ventures Among Business Education Students In Tertiary Institutions In Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined entrepreneurship mindsets as correlates with startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three research questions and tested three hypotheses. This study adopted correlational research design. The population of this study comprised 1165 students of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Taro Yamane's formula was used to get a sample size of 298 business students. The study made use of two instruments for data collection: the Entrepreneurship Mindset Questionnaire (EMQ) and Startup Venture Questionnaire (SVQ). Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used to determine the reliability. The reliability test yielded a coefficient of 0.81 for Cluster I, 0.80 for Cluster II and 0.83 for Cluster III. The study had an average reliability coefficient of 0.81. Data collected from the respondents were analysed with Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. The study found that students who are proactive in identifying opportunities, creative in developing new ideas and committed to continuous growth demonstrate higher tendencies to initiate and sustain entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, strengthening these entrepreneurial mindsets within tertiary institutions is essential for enhancing students' startup readiness, promoting economic participation and building a vibrant youth-driven entrepreneurial ecosystem in Delta State. Based on the findings, the study recommended that tertiary institutions should integrate entrepreneurship training that emphasizes opportunity recognition, creative thinking and growth-oriented learning into business education curricula. Government and school management should establish incubation hubs, innovation labs and mentorship programmes to nurture students' innovation- and growth-driven mindsets.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship Mindset, Startups, Startup Ventures

INTRODUCTION

The economy of a country like Nigeria plays a fundamental role in shaping national development, resource allocation and livelihood sustainability, as it influences employment creation and overall productivity. Scholars argue that the resilience of any economy depends on its ability to diversify production, stimulate innovation and support small-scale enterprises capable of driving societal transformation (Ndiomaluke, et. al., 2025). However, Nigeria's economy continues to face structural weaknesses arising from overdependence on oil, poor industrialization and fluctuating monetary policies (Afolabi, 2022). These challenges have generated far-reaching social consequences, thereby constraining

inclusive growth and job creation. Consequently, one of the most visible outcomes of Nigeria's unstable economic environment is rising unemployment.

Nigeria's unemployment rate has remained persistently high over the past decade, reflecting the inability of available economic opportunities to absorb the fast-growing labour force. Reports indicate that rising youth unemployment, in particular, is partly driven by skills mismatch, inadequate industrial expansion and insufficient government interventions (Abdulrazaq & Lambe, 2024). As the labour market continues to shrink, young Nigerians increasingly seek alternative economic pathways for survival. The high rate of graduate unemployment is almost 1.8 million yearly, which one of the greatest problems facing the country is the growing number of job seekers, with an unemployed majority among its youth population. From the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) as Uddin (2013) reported, the figure of unemployment in Nigeria was highest among youth between 15 to 24 and 25 to 44 and the problem is more serious in rural areas. Consequently, unemployment dialogue in Nigeria has been on the rise, increasing from 21.1% in 2010, to 23.9% in 2011, then 18.3% in 2016, to 18.8% in 2017, 23.1% in 2018 to 33.3% in 2020, 37.7% in 2022 and 40.6 in 2023 (National Statistics Bureau 2010-2023). This observation shows in Nigeria today that unemployment has created different youth social vices and crimes in a bid to put food on their tables.

According to Virk, et. al, (2023), the rising unemployment rate among graduates is believed to be largely responsible for rising crime such as internet fraud, kidnapping, armed robbery, prostitution, cultism, occultism, human ritual, riots, drug abuse and child trafficking. Virk, et. al, (2023) further stated that it is believed that these crimes are the results of insecurity in the country. This is in line with Gar and Rodgers (2020) who asserted that the unemployment scenario has continued to pose various challenges to the survival of the Nigerian nation. Nduka further stated that unemployment contributed to the increase in crimes and other social vices experienced in our society in recent times. From the Business Times Newspapers of February 2022, one of the critical issues that affects the Nigerian government today is youths' unemployment. This has social, economic and political implications on the economic growth and development of the country.

Unemployment in Nigeria has contributed negatively; poverty, oil production disruption due to pipeline vandalization by unemployed youth, emergence of indiscriminate groups such as Boko Haram, an unknown government and Niger Delta armed groups among others. These have led to unproductive workforce, contributes to low GDP, brings about psychological trauma, threatens family support and leads to strife, have negative effect on health and political instability. Economic analysts suggest that one viable response to this persistent unemployment crisis is the creation of innovative economic opportunities that allow young people to establish self-sustaining economic outlets (Uchechukwu, et. al., 2023). Therefore, in recent years, increasing attention has shifted towards encouraging startup ventures.

Startup ventures have been defined as newly established business initiatives created by individuals who identify market opportunities and design innovative solutions to commercialize them (Chidiebere, et. al., 2014). This definition emphasises novelty, risk-taking and the pursuit of scalable growth within competitive markets. Another definition describes startup ventures as small, flexible, early-stage enterprises founded with limited resources but structured to test new ideas, validate assumptions and adapt to changing consumer needs (Ajufo, 2013). This explanation highlights experimentation, growth potential and strategic learning as distinguishing characteristics. Both definitions underscore the entrepreneurial orientation required to develop new products or services and they further support the argument that startup ventures provide alternative job opportunities in unstable economic climates.

In a struggling economy like Nigeria, startup ventures are increasingly becoming instruments for reducing unemployment, addressing income inequality and stimulating innovation. Many analysts argue that startups contribute significantly to economic revival by exploiting emerging markets, utilizing local resources and providing flexible business models suited for unstable environments (Ofor, 2023). Despite infrastructural constraints, limited funding and inconsistent policy frameworks, Nigerian youths are establishing diverse startup enterprises driven by necessity and aspiration. This trend appears to offer new economic prospects that complement formal employment structures. In particular, the growth of startup

initiatives among young people reinforces the need for skills-based education and entrepreneurial training, especially within institutions of higher learning in Nigeria.

Institutions of higher learning are crucial to national development because they produce human capital, support research and promote innovation necessary for economic competitiveness. Higher education provides students with essential knowledge, problem-solving abilities and practical competencies required for addressing socio-economic challenges such as job creation, wealth generation and industrial growth (Olofin, et. al., 2023). Through structured curricular and experiential learning, universities and colleges help equip learners with the analytical and managerial skills necessary to participate meaningfully in the economy. As unemployment increases, higher education institutions have become more strategic in fostering entrepreneurship-related skills that empower graduates to create jobs rather than depend solely on formal employment, thereby fostering an entrepreneurship mindset among business education students.

The entrepreneurship mindset has been defined as a cognitive orientation characterized by creativity, opportunity recognition, resilience and willingness to take calculated risks in pursuing business ideas (Odia & Odia, 2013). This definition emphasizes psychological readiness and innovative thinking as drivers of entrepreneurial action. Another definition describes the entrepreneurship mindset as an attitudinal and behavioural framework that enables individuals to identify value-creating opportunities, mobilize resources and overcome barriers in the business environment (Obute, 2021). This explanation highlights adaptability, critical thinking and proactive decision-making as essential attributes. Together, these definitions show that developing the entrepreneurship mindset is vital for preparing business education students for self-employment in competitive and uncertain economic conditions.

There are three major types of entrepreneurship mindset commonly discussed in literature: the opportunity-driven mindset, the innovation-driven mindset and the growth-driven mindset. The opportunity-driven mindset focuses on identifying viable economic gaps; the innovation-driven mindset emphasizes creativity and new solutions; while the growth-driven mindset prioritizes scaling enterprises for long-term sustainability. These categories collectively expand the conceptual understanding of entrepreneurial thinking and establish the foundational behaviours necessary for startup development. Consequently, exploring these mindsets allows researchers to better understand entrepreneurial performance among students.

The opportunity-driven mindset correlates strongly with the establishment of startup ventures because individuals with this mindset are naturally inclined to identify unmet needs and emerging markets. Scholars argue that opportunity-oriented individuals are more likely to initiate new ventures since their behaviour aligns with proactive scanning of the environment and willingness to explore new possibilities (Bamidele, 2020). Their ability to identify viable economic gaps predicts their capacity to create new business models. This mindset fosters resilience and adaptability in unstable economic conditions, which are essential elements for startup success. The next paragraph examines the innovation-driven and growth-driven mindsets in relation to startup ventures.

The innovation-driven mindset influences startup ventures because it empowers individuals to generate creative ideas, design unique products and apply problem-solving strategies that improve competitiveness. Researchers observe that innovation-oriented individuals are better positioned to differentiate their startups from competitors through novelty and continuous improvement. Similarly, the growth-driven mindset correlates with startups that aim to expand, diversify and develop sustainable business structures, as individuals with this mindset prioritize long-term scalability (Ajeniwani, et. al., 2024). When combined, these mindsets strengthen the ability of startup founders to survive, innovate and grow despite economic constraints. The next paragraph discusses problems affecting entrepreneurship mindset development.

Despite the importance of entrepreneurship mindset training in tertiary institutions, several problems hinder its full development among business education students in Delta State, Nigeria. Scholars identify challenges such as theory-based teaching, inadequate practical exposure, poor funding of entrepreneurship programmes and limited access to real-world business incubation platforms (Ikpesu,,

2014). Furthermore, infrastructural deficits, lack of mentorship, limited digital literacy and insufficient industry collaboration weaken students' ability to convert entrepreneurial ideas into functional startup ventures. These challenges reduce the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education and limit students' readiness for self-employment. Consequently, business education graduates struggle to apply entrepreneurial mindsets within competitive economic environments, thereby constraining startup creation.

Statement of the Problem

Business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State in an ideal situation, should develop strong entrepreneurship mindsets that enable them to identify opportunities, innovate and establish viable startup ventures capable of reducing unemployment and enhancing economic development. However, in reality, many students still lack adequate entrepreneurial orientation due to theory-driven instruction, limited practical exposure, weak institutional support, poor access to funding and insufficient mentorship, which collectively hinder their capacity to initiate or sustain startup ventures. These challenges raise concerns about the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education and its ability to translate into real business creation. Therefore, it becomes necessary to investigate how entrepreneurship mindsets correlate with startup ventures among these students.

Objectives of the Study

1. Examine the relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria
2. Determine the relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria
3. Ascertain the relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria
2. There is no significant relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria
3. There is no significant relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

RESEARCH METHODS

This study adopted correlational research design. The population of this study comprised 1165 students of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Taro Yamane's formula was used to get a sample size of 298 business students. The study made use of two instruments for data collection: the Entrepreneurship Mindset Questionnaire (EMQ) and Startup Venture Questionnaire (SVQ). The instruments for data collection were a self-structured questionnaire. The Entrepreneurship Mindset Questionnaire (EMQ) was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A sought demographic variables of the respondents. Section B was divided into three Clusters, I, II and III. Cluster I sought the information on the opportunity-driven mindset. Cluster II sought the information on an innovation-driven mindset. Cluster III sought the information on a growth-driven mindset. Each of the clusters contained 10 items structured on a 4-point rating scale on Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). On the other hand, the second instrument, Startup Venture Questionnaire (SVQ) sought

information on the startup venture. This instrument contained 15 items structured on a 4-point rating scale on Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The face-to-face method of data collection was used to collect data from the respondents. Twenty (20) business education students in tertiary institutions in Edo State were used to test the reliability of the instrument using a trial test. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used to determine the reliability. The reliability test yielded a coefficient of 0.81 for Cluster I, 0.80 for Cluster II and 0.83 for Cluster III. The study had an average reliability coefficient of 0.81. At the end of the exercise, 244 copies out of the 298 copies administered to the students were retrieved. This gave a return rate of 81.88% for the data collected. Data collected from the respondents were analysed with Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. Thus, the scales of measurement of this study include:

Very Strong Relationship	-	0.90 - 1.00
Strong Relationship	-	0.70 - 0.89
Moderate	-	0.50 - 0.69
Very Low Relationship	-	0.30 - 0.49
Negligible	-	0.01 - 0.29

More so, when the p-value is equal to or less than 0.05 level of significance, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, when the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the alternative hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted.

RESULTS

Research question One: *What is the relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: The relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

Variables	N	Startup Ventures	Opportunity-Driven Mindset	Remark
Startup Ventures	298	1	.800**	Strong Relationship
Opportunity-Driven Mindset	298	.800**	1	

Table 1 shows the relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The results revealed that the r-value was 0.80. This implies there is a strong relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

Research question Two: *What is the relationship between the innovation-driven and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: The relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and entrepreneurship mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

Variables	N	Startup Ventures	Innovation-Driven Mindset	Remark
Startup Ventures	298	1	.807**	Strong Relationship
Innovation-Driven Mindset	298	.807**	1	

Table 2 shows the relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The results revealed that the r-value was 0.807. This implies that there is a strong relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and entrepreneurship mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

Research question Three: *What is the relationship between the growth-driven mindset and entrepreneurship mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: The relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup venture among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

Variables	N	Startup Ventures	Growth-Driven Mindset	Remark
Startup Ventures	298	1	.823**	Strong Relationship
Growth-Driven Mindset	298	.823**	1	

Table 3 shows the relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The results revealed that the r-value was 0.823. This implies that there is a strong relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Test of Hypothesis One

Variables	N	Startup Ventures	Opportunity-Driven Mindset	P-Value	Remark
Startup Ventures	298	1	.800**	0.00	Significant
Opportunity-Driven Mindset	298	.800**	1		

Table 5 shows the test of hypothesis one on the relationship between the opportunity-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The results revealed that the r-value was 0.80. The p-value was 0.000, which is below 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that opportunity-driven mindset has a significant strong positive relationship with startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Test of Hypothesis Two

Variables	N	Startup Ventures	Innovation-Driven Mindset	P-Value	Remark
Startup Ventures	298	1	.807**	0.00	Significant
Innovation-Driven Mindset	298	.807**	1		

Table 6 shows the test of hypothesis two on the relationship between the innovation-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The results revealed that the r-value was 0.807. The p-value was 0.000, which is below 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that innovation-driven mindset has a significant strong positive relationship with startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

Table 3: Test of Hypothesis Three

Variables	N	Startup Ventures	Growth-Driven Mindset	P-Value	Remark
Startup Ventures	298	1	.823**	0.00	Significant
Growth-Driven Mindset	298	.823**	1		

Table 3 shows the test of hypothesis three on the relationship between the growth-driven mindset and startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The results revealed that the r-value was 0.823. The p-value was 0.000, which is below 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that growth-driven mindset has a significant strong positive relationship with startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of research question one and test of hypothesis one showed that opportunity-driven mindset has a significant strong positive relationship with startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. This finding suggests that students who possess a proactive orientation toward identifying, evaluating and exploiting business opportunities are more likely to initiate entrepreneurial activities. This positive association implies that the cognitive disposition to recognize gaps in the market, envision innovative solutions and take calculated risks directly enhances students' likelihood of launching new ventures. It further indicates that entrepreneurial behaviour among these students is not solely motivated by necessity or survival pressures but by strategic pursuit of value creation, competitive advantage and long-term business prospects. Thus, cultivating an opportunity-driven mindset becomes central to fostering entrepreneurship in educational contexts.

This finding aligns with prior scholarly submissions that emphasize the predictive role of opportunity-driven cognition in entrepreneurial engagement. For instance, Nafukho and El Mansour (2025) found that opportunity recognition skills significantly influence students' participation in venture creation processes. Similarly, Diepolder, Weitzel and Huwer (2024) reported that students with an opportunity-oriented outlook demonstrate higher entrepreneurial intention and resilience in business development. In another study, Viswanath, P., Annapally and Kumar (2024) noted that opportunity-seeking behaviour enhances innovative thinking and increases the likelihood of successful startup formation among undergraduates. These corroborating studies reinforce the conclusion that opportunity-driven mindset is a strong determinant of students' entrepreneurial behaviour.

The findings of research question two and test of hypothesis two showed that innovation-driven mindset has a significant strong positive relationship with startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. This finding indicated that students who are inclined toward creativity, experimentation and novel problem-solving are more likely to initiate entrepreneurial projects. This implies that the ability to generate fresh ideas, rethink existing processes and develop unique products or services substantially enhances students' willingness and capacity to launch startups. The strength of the relationship suggests that innovation is not merely an optional entrepreneurial attribute but

a core psychological driver that shapes students' entrepreneurial behaviour, competitiveness and sustainability of their ventures. Thus, cultivating an innovation-driven mindset becomes essential for stimulating vibrant startup ecosystems within tertiary institutions.

This result is consistent with earlier empirical studies emphasizing the role of innovation orientation in promoting entrepreneurial action. For example, Moses (2025) found that students with strong innovative tendencies exhibit greater likelihood of venture creation and persistence in business development. Similarly, Abiodun, Daodu, Eniolorunda and James (2024) reported that innovation-driven cognition significantly predicts entrepreneurial intention and successful opportunity exploitation among business undergraduates. In another related study, Osanyinlusi (2024) argued that innovation orientation enhances creativity, risk-taking and business model development, thereby increasing the probability of startup establishment. These studies collectively corroborate the conclusion that an innovation-driven mindset is a critical determinant of students' startup engagement.

The findings of research question three and test of hypothesis three indicated that growth-driven mindset has a significant strong positive relationship with startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. This finding indicated that students who demonstrate a persistent desire for personal development, continuous learning and long-term achievement are more inclined to initiate entrepreneurial activities. This suggests that individuals who view challenges as opportunities for improvement, embrace feedback and exhibit resilience in the face of uncertainty are more likely to engage in venture creation. The strong positive relationship further implies that students' willingness to pursue scalable ideas, expand their entrepreneurial capacity and invest in progressive business models significantly enhances their likelihood of establishing and sustaining startup ventures. Consequently, nurturing a growth-driven mindset becomes a key driver in building an entrepreneurial culture within tertiary institutions.

This finding is supported by prior empirical studies that underscore the relevance of growth-oriented psychological traits in entrepreneurial behaviour. For instance, David, Obisanya, Ogunyemi and Ojo (2025) reported that students with strong growth mindsets exhibit higher entrepreneurial inclination and stronger commitment to venture creation. Similarly, Moses (2025) found that a growth-driven orientation significantly predicts students' persistence, innovation capacity and willingness to initiate business startups. In addition, Ogunsola (2025) observed that a growth-focused mindset enhances strategic thinking, opportunity expansion and long-term business planning among undergraduates. These studies collectively reinforce the conclusion that a growth-driven mindset is a crucial determinant of students' startup engagement.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that opportunity-driven, innovation-driven and growth-driven mindsets collectively play significant and strongly positive roles in predicting startup ventures among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Students who are proactive in identifying opportunities, creative in developing new ideas and committed to continuous growth demonstrate higher tendencies to initiate and sustain entrepreneurial activities. These findings highlight that successful venture creation is influenced by cognitive orientations that foster opportunity recognition, innovation capacity, resilience and long-term strategic thinking. Therefore, strengthening these entrepreneurial mindsets within tertiary institutions is essential for enhancing students' startup readiness, promoting economic participation and building a vibrant youth-driven entrepreneurial ecosystem in Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Tertiary institutions should integrate entrepreneurship training that emphasizes opportunity recognition, creative thinking and growth-oriented learning into business education curricula.
2. Government and school management should establish incubation hubs, innovation labs and mentorship programmes to nurture students' innovation- and growth-driven mindsets.

3. Lecturers should adopt experiential teaching methods such as business simulations, startup challenges and problem-based learning to strengthen students' opportunity-driven entrepreneurial capabilities.

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